

FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL FACE WASH

¹*Mr. R. S. Doshi, ²Miss. Sakshi Chandrakant Padalkar, ³Miss. Sakshi Gajanan
Dahidule

Department of Pharmaceuticals, Satara College of Pharmacy, Satara, Affiliated to Dbatu,
Lorene, Maharashtra.

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***Corresponding Author**

Mr. R. S. Doshi

Department of Pharmaceuticals,
Satara College of Pharmacy, Satara,
Affiliated to Dbatu, Lorene,
Maharashtra

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ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to develop an effective herbal face wash formulation and evaluate its physicochemical, organoleptic, and performance parameters. All the ingredients were selected based on their natural cleansing, antioxidant, and skin-soothing properties. The formulated face wash was evaluated for various parameters such as color, Oduor, appearance, pH, foamability, spread ability and washability. The formulation exhibited a brownish color, smooth fragrance, smooth appearance and good foamability. The pH of the formulation was found to be $5.8 \pm 6.5 \pm 0.2$, which is within the skin-friendly range. The spread ability was 20 ± 35 g.cm/sec indicating easy application. The face wash was easily washable with water without leaving any residue. No irritation, redness, or any dermatological effects were observed during irritation testing. The results demonstrated that the herbal face wash

possesses satisfactory physicochemical stability and effective cleansing action, making it a suitable and safe cosmetic product for daily use.

KEYWORDS: Herbal face wash, Formulation, Evaluation, pH, Foamability, Spread ability, Washability, Skin-friendly, Natural ingredients.

INTRODUCTION

The word Cosmetics is taken from a greek word "Kosmeticos", which means to 'adorn' (addition of something decorative to a person or a thing) Since early days materials used for

beautification or improvement of appearance comes under the category of cosmetics. People want to look beautiful, and the concept of Cosmetics is as old as mankind and civilization. The urge to beautify one's own body and look beautiful has been an urge in humans since the tribal days. Assorted beauty products such as skincare products, hair products, fragrances, oral hygiene and nail products. Cosmetics are products applied to the body for the purpose of beautifying, cleansing or improving appearance and enhancing attractive features. Cosmetics consist of a large range of products such as toothpaste, shampoo, conditioners, mascara after shave lotion, styling gel, creams, facewash, powders. Perfumes, lipsticks. Finger nail and toe nail polish, eye and facial make-up, hair wavers. hair dyes Sprays deodorants and antiperspirants. The word "make- up" is defined as a cosmetic which refers primarily to colored product intended to alter the user appearance schneider et al defined skincare product or cosmetics as mixtures of synthetic or natural chemical compound used to improve the appearance and smell of the body. Skin is a major part of body and face skin is one of the sensitive and representative parameter human personality. The increasing awareness of the harmful effect of synthetic chemicals in skin care products has led to a growing demand for natural and herbal alternatives among these, herbal face wash has gained popularity as a chemical free, ecofriendly, skin friendly cleansing solution. Unlike conventional liquid face wash that contains sulfates, parabens and artificial fragrance, herbal cleansers utilize natural ingredients to clean, exfoliate and nourish the skin in recent years, there has been a significant shift towards natural and herbal skincare products due to concerns the long-term effect of synthetic chemical in conventional cosmetics.^[1]

Types of cosmetics

A) According to region

- 1 Skin - Powder, lipstick, rough, lotion, etc.
- 2 Hair – Shampoo, conditioner, bleach, cream.
- 3 Nails – Nail paint, nail paint remover, etc.
- 4 Teeth – Powder, paste, gel and dentifrices etc.
- 5 Eye – Eyeliner, mascara, eyeshadows, and eyebrow pencil etc.

B) According to function

- 1 Emollient preparation – Cold cream, vanishing cream, lotion and solution etc.
- 2 Cleansing preparation – Shampoo, face wash, body wash, hand wash, soap.
- 3 Decorative preparation – Lipstick, eyeliner

- 4 Protective preparation – Sunscreen, cream, powder
- 5 Preparation for enjoyment – Salt powder oil and milk

C) According to compositions

- 1 Powder
- 2 Lotion
- 3 Emulsion
- 4 Solution
- 5 Suspension
- 6 Cream
- 7 Pastes
- 8 Gel
- 9 Aerosol
- 10 Pencils
- 11 Sticks

Different types of face washes

- 1 Cream based face wash
- 2 Gel based face wash
- 3 Liquid face wash
- 4 Face wash in powder form

Properties of face wash

- 1 It should remove dead cells.
- 2 It should rejuvenate the skin cells.
- 3 It should remove oil, dirt and impurities.
- 4 Leave skin fresh and breathing.
- 5 It should be washed off easily^[23]

Material use in face wash

Properties Fig. no. 1: Banana peels.

Banana peels

Classification

- Scientific name - *Musa acuminata*
- Family - Musaceae
- Order – zingiberales
- Kingdom- plantae
- Genus – Musa
- Banana peel is rich in antioxidants, fiber and essential nutrients and helps Brighten the skin and reduce wrinkles.
- Acts as a moisturizer and helps in hydrating the skin.
- It is anti-inflammatory.^[23]

Red turmeric

Properties Fig. no. 2: Red turmeric.

Classification

- Scientific name: *Curcuma longa*
- Kingdom: Plantae
- Order: Zingiberales
- Family: Zingiberene
- Genus: *Curcuma*
- high-strength anti-inflammatory
- antioxidant and antimicrobial properties.^[15]

Coriander leaves

Fig. no. 3: Coriander leaves.

Classification

- Scientific name: Coriandrum
- Kingdom: Plantae
- Order: Apiales
- Family: Apiaceae (Umbelliferae) Properties
- Antioxidant.^[15]

Linseed

Fig. no. 4: Linseed.

Classification

- Scientific name – flax
- Order – Malpighi ales
- Kingdom – plantae
- Genus - Linum Properties
- Combats fine lines and wrinkles.
- Protect skin from acne.
- Soothes skin irritation.
- Moisturizes skin.
- Skin rejuvenation.^[23]

Lemon

Fig. no. 5: Lemon.

Classification

- Scientific name: Citrus lemon
- Kingdom: Plantae
- Order: Sapindales
- Family: Rosacea
- Genus: Citrus Properties
- Oil control and astringent properties.
- Brightening and fading marks.
- Exfoliation.^[23]

Reetha powder

Fig. no. 6: Reetha powder.

Classification

- Scientific name: Sapindus mukorossi
- Family: Sapindaceae Properties
- Skin health
- Foaming.^[23]

Equipment used

Table no. 1.

Sr. No.	Glass-Ware	Apparatus
1	Funnel	Hot Air Oven
2	Glass Rod	Magnetic Stirrer
3	Measuring Cylinder	PH Meter
4	Beaker	
5	Morter Pestle	
6	Viscometer	

Preparation of Herbal Face Wash

Collection

Herbal and Chemicals which were used in presence study were collected from local area and

purchased from market

- 1 Banana Peel
- 2 Red Turmeric
- 3 Coriander Leaves
- 4 Linseed
- 5 Lemon
- 6 Fragrance
- 7 Reetha Powder

Preparation of Herbal Extract

Banana Peel, Red Turmeric, Coriander Leaves were cleaned thoroughly to removed dirt/silt particles. And were in shade for drying then they were grounded to a powder by using grinder and then extract of each herb was made with the help of distilled water and kept them in which were the conical flasks. were Shaked for 24 hours. After 1day contents were filtered out by using simple filtration method and filtrate were collected in vessels separately and then evaporated in water bath and a concentrated solution was made.^[11]

Table no. 2.

Sr. no.	Content	Formula
1	Banana Peel	10ml
2	Red Turmeric	5ml
3	Coriander Leaves	5ml
4	Linseed	10ml
5	Lemon	0.5ml
6	Fragrance	1-2 drop
7	Reetha Powder	10gm

Evaluation Parameter of Herbal face wash

1)Physical evaluation

Procedure

1. Take a small quantity of herbal face wash in a clean beaker.
2. Observe visually under normal light.
3. Note the colour, clarity, and presence of any particles.

2) pH

Procedure

1. Switch on pH meter and allow it to warm up.

2. Ensure the electrode clean and properly connected.
3. Rinse the electrode with distilled water
4. Gently blot dry.

3) Washability- Procedure

1. Take a small amount of face wash
2. Apply on the skin
3. Allow it to remain for a few minutes
4. Wash the applied area with a gentle of water
5. Observe how easily the face wash is removed

4) Spreadability- Procedure

1. Take clean glass slides and place a known quantity of face wash at the center
2. Place another glass slide gently over the sample to form a uniform film
3. Place a specific weight on the upper slide for about 1-2 minutes to ensure uniform thickness
4. Tie a thread to the upper slide and attach a small weight to pull it horizontally
5. Remove the weight placed on top
6. Start the stopwatch and allow the upper slide to move due to the pulling weight
7. Record the time taken for the upper slide to move a fixed distance

5) Foamability

Procedure

1. Take 1g of face wash
2. Transfer it into 100 ml measuring cylinder
3. Shake the cylinder vigorously for 10-15 times
4. Immediately note the volume(foam)
5. Allow the cylinder to stand undisturbed for 5min
6. Measure foam volume after 5 min ^[14].

RESULT

The formulated herbal face wash was evaluated at different parameters. All the organoleptic properties were checked visually such as, color, Oduor, PH, foamability, spread ability, washability, Appearance and nature. As a result, the colour of Formulation is brownish, no bad smell occurred from the formulation. washability and cleansing properties of herbal facewash was found to be good, and it is easily removed by washing with normal water it left a smooth

feel on the skin after washing and no dryness was observed. Spreadability quantity was also tested with the help of glass plate and was easily spreadable when compared with a marketed gel-based face wash. No irritation, redness or any dermatological effects were observed on skin during irritancy testing

Table no. 3.

Sr.no	Test	Result
1	Color	Brownish
2	Oduor	Smooth Fragrances
3	Appearance	Smooth
4	Nature	Smooth
5	pH	5.8±6.5±0.2
6	Foamability	Good
7	Washability	Easily Washable
8	Spredability	20±35 g.cm/sec

1) Physical evaluation- Colour- Brownish

Odour – Smooth fragrance

Appearance- Smooth

2) pH-The pH of the herbal face wash found to be in the range of 5.8±6.5±0.2

3) Foamability- The formulation produced adequate foam on shaking

Good foamability indicate effective cleansing action of the face wash Height of Foam- 2cm.

4) Washability – The prepared face wash was easily removed with normal water Without leaving any residue on the skin showing good washability.

5) Spredability – The formulation spread uniformly on the skin with minimal effort Good spreadability ensures easy application and better coverage skin.

CONCLUSION

The herbal face wash formulation was successfully prepared and evaluated for various parameters such as appearance, pH, foamability, spreadability, washability, and skin compatibility. The results showed that the formulation possessed good cleansing action, acceptable foaming properties, and a skin-friendly ph. The presence of herbal ingredients provides additional benefits such as nourishment, moisturization, antioxidant activity, and protection against skin problems with minimal side effects.

Future perspective

1. Herbal face wash has a bright future because people are becoming more aware about skin health

2. In future, the demand for herbal cosmetics is expected to increase due to growing interest in organic and Ayurvedic product
3. Herbal face wash can also be developed for different skin types such as oily, dry, sensitive, and acne-prone skin.
4. herbal face wash has good commercial value and great potential in the cosmetic and pharmaceutical industries.
5. Advanced packaging and preservation techniques may also increase product shelf life.
6. consumers prefer natural and herbal products because they are safer, gentle on the skin, and eco-friendly.

REFERENCE

- 1 Khan, A.D.*1, and Alam, M.N.1 cosmetic and their associated adverse effects.
- 2 Malik, Vijay., the drug and cosmetics act, 1940, 18th edition, new Delhi: eastern book company pp 5-6.
- 3 Darel's, Z.D., Cosmetics: the medicine of beauty journal of cosmetic dermatology, 2015; 14(2): 91.
- 4 Schneider, G., Gohla, S., Schreiber, Kaden, W., Schmock, U., Lewer Kuhne, H.S., Kuschel, A., petites, X., Pape, W., Ippon, H., Diem beak, W., in skin cosmetics, Ullmann's encyclopedia of industrial chemistry 6th vol. Germany: Wiley VCH, 2001; 10: 24-29.
- 5 Lal, B.B., the Saraswati flows on the continuity of Indian culture., 2002; 56-57.
- 6 Kanitakis, J., anatomy histology and immunohistochemistry of normal human skin, European Journal of dermatology., 2002; 12(4): 390-401
- 7 Brown, S.K., Shalita, A., Acne vulgarism, lancet, 1998; 351(9119): 1871 – 1876.
- 8 Kapoor, V. P., herbal cosmetics for skin and hair care, national botanical research institute., 2005; 4(4): 306-313.
- 9 Ashish, Baldi., herbal cosmetics: used for skin and hair invent rapid journals, 2012; (1): 1-7.
- 10 Harsharan, pal, Singh, et al. anti-acne synergistic herbal face wash gel. World journal of pharmaceutical research vol.4, Issue (IX), (2015).
- 11 Nitin Yadav et al. formulation and development of face wash journal of emerging technologies and innovative research vol. 6, Issue (VI), (2021).
- 12 Martha Srinivas, et al. current review on herbal face care. international journal of pharmaceutical sciences review and research article no., 17: (2021).

- 13 Saud agar R.B., Sisodia M.H. Review on herbal cosmetics; 7(7): 573-591.
- 14 Divya P, Puthusseri B, Neelwarne B, Carotenoid content, its stability during the drying and antioxidant activity of commercial coriander varieties. Food Research International, 2012; 45(1): 342-50.
- 15 Vasoya Dhruval, Vasava Nehali, Vazara Ronak, Vaishali Sharma, Dhananjay Meshram, Formulation Evaluation and stability study of facewash containing polyherbal extract. Research, (2021); 10(9).
- 16 Yadav Shivkumar, Yadav Puyush, Yadav Deepa Kumar, Maurya Manish Kumar, Muhammed Nadeem, Fakir Muhammad Anjum, Muhammad Issa Kha, Sameena Tehsin, Nutritional and medicinal aspects of coriander. British Food Journal, (2013); 115(5): 743-755.
- 17 Jangra Satya shree, V.K. Kadam, Sigh Isha, Dushyant, Comparative analysis of Phytochemical profile and antioxidant activity of coriander (*Coriandrum Sativum L.*). Asian Journal of Chemistry (2018).
- 18 Vandar Ashish, Sheikh Rehana, Thombare Rajanee, Chivate Anirudh, Chivate Nirranjan, American
- 19 Gadgegone, S., et al. formulation and development of skin whitening face wash international journal of researches in biosciences, agriculture and technology vol. 5, Issue (II), (2017)
- 20 P.K.Mane and Aniket dangare herbal face wash gel of cynodont dactylon having antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory action pharmaceutical resonance vol.3, Issue(IX), (2020).
- 21 K. Kameswara rao et ai. Formulation and evaluation of poly herbal anti acne face wash international research journal of pharmaceutical and biosciences vol. 5, Issue (II), (2019).
- 22 Dr. Vandna Pathak¹, Shikha Shukla Formulation of face wash using natural herb international journal of novel research and development vol 7, Issue (2022).